

Valorisation of Banana and Pineapple Peel Wastes for Sustainable Bioethanol Production: An Integrated Assessment of Fermentation Efficiency, Ethanol Quality, and Energy Recovery

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Abstract

Production of bioethanol from agricultural waste has become interesting owing to the growing need for sustainable fuel and environmental issues associated with the disposal of fruit waste. The aim of this research was to evaluate the potential of pineapple (*Ananas comosus*) and banana (*Musa paradisiaca*) peel as bioethanol production through acid hydrolysis and fermentation process using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. The dried fruit peel biomass (50 g) was hydrolysed with 1 M sulfuric acid and then fermented for seven days, and ethanol was recovered by distillation. Ethanol yield, sugar content, biomass conversion efficiency, sugar utilisation efficiency, ethanol quality, fermentation stability, and potential for energy recovery were measured. Both peels had an equal ethanol yield of 20.0%, corresponding to 10mL of ethanol from 50g of biomass. The sugar content of Pineapple peels was 2.80%, yielding better ethanol quality based on an ethanol density of 0.80 g/mL, a density deviation of 1.39%, and approaching the optimum pH (5.60 pH) for fermentation. But banana peel had a higher biomass conversion efficiency of 0.180 g ethanol/g biomass, a higher sugar utilisation efficiency of 10.00, and a higher energy recovery potential of 4.82 MJ/kg biomass. The composite performance evaluation data indicated that the overall performance of pineapple peel was 91.5%, while that of banana peel was 91.2%. From the study, it can be inferred that both wastes of the fruits, namely pineapple peel and banana peel, are very good raw materials for the production of bioethanol as second-generation feedstocks and that pineapple peel is good as a feedstock for better quality bioethanol, and banana peel is good as feedstock to achieve better biomass to energy conversion efficiency. The outcomes can be used for the sustainable valorisation of waste, the generation of renewables and the circular bioeconomy.

Keywords: *Bioethanol production, Banana peels, Pineapple peels, Biomass conversion efficiency, Renewable energy, Waste valorisation.*

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Introduction

Geographically, the growth of the population, urbanisation, and technological development is accelerating the world's demand for energy like never before, driven by a rapidly growing industry. Traditional energy sources, such as petroleum, coal, and natural gas, have been used extensively for decades in the transportation sector, industry, and power generation. These resources have contributed greatly to economic development, but their continuous utilisation has led to environmental degradation and the ensuing problems: global climate change and global warming, loss of biodiversity, impacts on non-biological environments, greenhouse gas emissions, etc. Furthermore, fossil fuels are finite resources, and as demand increases, their supply is declining, raising concerns about energy security and sustainability. Such difficulties have spurred an intensified research and development drive worldwide to find alternative renewable energy sources that can help meet current and future energy needs while reducing environmental impact. Biofuels appear to be a promising option among renewable energy technologies available today, since they can be derived from biological sources and used with minimal changes to existing fuel systems. Bioethanol, in particular, has attracted considerable interest due to its renewability, biodegradability, high octane number, and potential to reduce negative emissions when mixed with gasoline (Khairati, 2024; Acha *et al.*, 2025; Zabochnicka-Świątek & Sławik, 2010). Bioethanol is produced by fermenting sugars from biomass, which can be continuously replenished through cultivation, whereas fossil fuels can't. Production of bioethanol has increased considerably in recent years, with many countries taking steps to diversify energy supplies and to reduce carbon footprints. The capacity of food crops (corn, wheat, sugarcane) to produce bioethanol, however, is raising considerable concerns about food security, competition for land, rising food prices, and unsustainable resource use. As a result, the focus has turned to producing second-generation bioethanol from non-food biomaterials and agricultural residues. This will not only give them the opportunity to take action on human resources and other foods but also enable them to manage their waste sustainably. Therefore, the utilisation of agricultural and fruit wastes for bioethanol production has become an interesting alternative, not only for renewable energy development but also for environmental treatment and waste disposal. The study of BCWDF has become important, as it helps achieve major targets of the circular bioeconomy missions, environmentally friendly goals, and the energy security target to reduce carbon-rich greenhouse gases today, due to the increasing implementation of sustainable development frameworks.

Fruit wastes are among the richest and least valorised biomass resources that can be found around the world. Much of these fruit residues are generated during the growing operations, from backyard to household consumption, harvest, transport, and processing, on an annual basis. When considering solid waste from food, fruit and vegetable waste accounts for approximately 40-50% of the total food waste generated globally, according to recent estimates (Mgeni *et al.*, 2024). Sadly, most of this fruit waste goes into the open dump sites, landfills, is burned or decomposes naturally, which pollutes the environment, emits greenhouse gases and odours, and creates health problems. This kind of disposal poses environmental issues and causes the loss of a potentially valuable biomass resource that could be used for renewable energy production. Fruit peels are especially appealing feedstocks for bioethanol production, as they contain significant amounts of carbohydrates, cellulose, hemicellulose, starch, and

fermentable sugars that can be broken down hydrolytically and fermentatively to produce ethanol. Among the available fruit wastes, banana and pineapple peels have attracted considerable scientific interest due to their abundance, low cost, and biochemical composition. Banana Peel is approximately 30-40% by weight of the banana and contains a rich amount of fermentative carbohydrate, starch, Cellulose, protein and minerals to support microbial fermentation (Hikal *et al.*, 2022; Chinedu *et al.*, 2026a; Ejike *et al.*, 2012). In pineapple, the peels make up about 25 to 40% of the pineapple fruit mass, and it contains high levels of glucose, fructose, sucrose, cellulose, hemicellulose, vitamins and minerals, which makes it a good source of bioethanol (Mehraj *et al.*, 2024). Several fruit wastes have been shown to be potential feedstocks and able to be used to produce bioethanol in sustainability-friendly ways (Chinedu *et al.*, 2026b; Singh *et al.*, 2017; Ibe *et al.*, 2025; Chinedu *et al.*, 2024; Oiwoh *et al.*, 2018). But, changes in the substrate's composition, hydrolysis efficiency, fermentation results, sugar utilisation, and ethanol recovery still influence the production results. Hence, comparative investigations between different fruit wastes need to be conducted and comprehended as to which one is the best feedstock for bioethanol production? This is particularly important in the developing world, where fruit wastes are abundant, and energy supplies from renewable sources are limited, expensive and/or not easily available, which could be used for environmental and economic development.

While the fruit waste may serve as a potential feedstock for bioethanol production, the utilisation of fruit waste on a large scale is still relatively low and some challenges still exist that are putting hurdles to the large-scale utilisation of fruit wastes. Very few studies have been performed in this area, and those that have focused on identifying optimisation strategies for a specific feedstock and/or comparing the performance characteristics of the feedstocks under different experimental conditions. Besides, there are only a few limited data available on comparative efficiency in terms of ethanol yield, biomass conversion efficiency, sugar utilisation efficiency, ethanol recovery, fermentation stability, ethanol quality, and energy recovery potential of the banana peel and pineapple peel. This information is of paramount importance for identifying the best-adapted feedstocks for sustainable bioethanol production and is needed for data-driven policymaking on the use of biomass resources. Furthermore, increased awareness of the circular economy concept has shifted the vision toward the mission of turning agricultural waste into value-added products that generate economic, environmental, and social benefits. Thus, the objectives are achieved directly by converting fruit peels into bioethanol, reducing environmental burden, generating renewable energy, and valorising waste. Hence, the aim of this study is to produce “Bioethanol” using fruit wastes (BP and PP) through acid hydrolysis and fermentation process. Specifically, the objectives of this study are the collection and preparation of Banana Peels and Pineapple Peels for bioethanol production, hydrolysis of the collected biomass to obtain fermentable sugars, fermentation of the hydrolysates with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, determination of the yield, quality and density of the bioethanol obtained, calculation of biomass conversion efficiency, calculation of sugar utilisation efficiency, determination of ethanol recovery, determination of bioenergy potential and comparison of the overall performance of the feedstocks through integrated performance assessment techniques. They are expected to contribute to the growing body of information on second-generation bioethanol production, valuable know-how about successful waste management practices, as well as supporting data for sustainable renewable energy development and utilisation of fruit-processing wastes as alternative sources for achieving environmental sustainability and energy security (Mgeni *et al.*, 2024; Khairati, 2024; Ahanor *et al.*, 2025; Chinedu *et al.*, 2026c; Isangadighi *et al.*, 2026).

Methodology

Research Design

The research design used in this study was an experimental laboratory study, which aimed to analyse the potential of selected fruit wastes for bioethanol production, including pineapple and banana peels (*Musa*

paradisiaca). Collection and preparation of fruit peels (experimental raw material), acid hydrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass to produce fermentable sugars, fermentation of the hydrolysates into ethanol using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, bioethanol distillation, assessment of bioethanol yield, biomass conversion efficiency, sugar utilisation, energy recovery potential, bioethanol quality, and evaluation of the performances of the feedstocks were carried out by the experimental approach. To assess the suitability of both fruit wastes as renewable feedstocks for sustainable bioethanol production, comparative analyses were performed.

Study Area

The study was carried out in Ozoro, and all analyses were carried out at the Chemistry Laboratory of the Department of Chemistry, Southern Delta University (SDE), Ozoro, Delta State, Nigeria. Laboratory analyses, hydrolysis, fermentation and distillation were carried out under laboratory-controlled conditions.

Materials and Reagents

The materials used for the study consisted of fresh banana peels, pineapple peels, distilled water, sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4), sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution, baker's yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*), Fehling's solution, filter papers, fermentation bottles and laboratory glassware.

Equipment

The apparatus used comprised analytical weighing balance, blender, drying oven, thermometer, pH meter, measuring cylinder, conical flask, beaker, hot plate, heating mantle, distillation apparatus, hydrometer, filtration unit, fermentation containers and laboratory stirrers.

Sample Collection and Preparation

Banana and pineapple peels were harvested from fruit sellers in Ozoro metropolis and were freshly harvested. The peels were thoroughly washed with distilled water to wash away impurities and mire. The peels, after being cleaned, were cut into small pieces to increase surface area, then sun-dried and oven-dried for 2 weeks until dry to a constant weight. The dried samples were ground in a laboratory blender to ensure fine biomass powder for the hydrolysis process. In each experimental treatment, a known amount of biomass (50 g) was dried.

Acid Hydrolysis of Fruit Peel Biomass

Each dried fruit peel sample was transferred to a 500 mL conical flask, with a sample mass of 50 g. To each flask, 200 mL of 1 M sulfuric acid was added. These mixtures were then heated at $100^\circ C$ for 60 minutes to hydrolyse the cellulose and hemicellulose into fermentable sugars. After hydrolysis, the products were cooled to room temperature and filtered through Whatman filter paper to separate the hydrolysates from the unhydrolyzed solids. Sodium hydroxide solution was used to redetermine the pH of the filtrates to a range suitable for yeast fermentation.

Fermentation Process

Fermentation of sugars for the production of ethanol was performed using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. Two grams (2 g) bakers yeast was activated in warm distilled water and left to sit for 15 minutes. The neutralised hydrolysates were then all inoculated with the activated yeast culture. Improved methods for sealing fermentation vessels with airlocking to prevent contamination, but allowing carbon dioxide from the fermentation to escape were used. The fermentation was conducted at the lab temperature ($28-32^\circ C$) for 7 days. Throughout the fermentation period, observable signs of active fermentation (gas evolution and foam formation) were monitored.

Ethanol Recovery by Distillation

After the fermentation, the fermentation broths were filtered to remove the suspended solids. After the filtration the filtrates have been distilled simply at boiling point of ethanol (78-80° C). Crude bioethanol was collected and measured from distillates produced. The amount of recovered ethanol that the volume and weight of was then noted for further analysis.

Determination of Physicochemical Parameters

Determination of Ethanol Volume

The ethanol recovered was measured in graduated measuring cylinders, and the volume of ethanol in milliliters (mL) was recorded.

Determination of Ethanol Weight

An analytical balance was used to measure the weighed amounts of the recovered ethanol samples and the values were noted in grams (g).

Determination of Ethanol Density

The density of recovered ethanol was determined by the hydrometer, and calculated mathematically as follows:

$$\text{Density} \left(\frac{g}{mL} \right) = \frac{\text{Weight of Ethanol (g)}}{\text{Volume of Ethanol (mL)}} \quad (1)$$

Determination of Sugar Content

The content of sugar was determined by Fehling's titration method and calculated as:

$$\text{Sugar Content (\%)} = \frac{\text{Volume of Fehling Solution used (mL)}}{\text{Volume of Sample Analyzed (mL)}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Determination of pH

Immediately after fermentation, the pH of the hydrolysates produced was determined through pH meter which was calibrated with standard buffers.

Determination of Bioethanol Yield and Derived Performance Indicators

Ethanol Yield

$$\text{Ethanol Yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Volume of Ethanol Produced (mL)}}{\text{Weight of Dried Biomass (g)}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Biomass Conversion Efficiency

$$\text{Biomass Conversion Energy} \left(\frac{g}{g} \right) = \frac{\text{Ethanol Weight (g)}}{\text{Dry Biomass Weight (g)}} \quad (4)$$

Sugar Utilization Efficiency Index

$$\text{Sugar Utilization Efficiency Index} = \frac{\text{Ethanol Yield (\%)}}{\text{Sugar Content (\%)}} \quad (5)$$

Ethanol Recovery Factor

The ethanol recovery factor was calculated using:

$$\text{Ethanol Recovery Factor} \left(\frac{\text{mL}}{\text{g}} \right) = \frac{\text{Ethanol Volume (mL)}}{\text{Dry Biogas (g)}} \quad (6)$$

Ethanol Productivity

The ethanol productivity per day was calculated as:

$$\text{Ethanol Productivity} \left(\frac{\text{mL}}{\text{day}} \right) = \frac{\text{Ethanol Volume Produced (mL)}}{\text{Fermentation Time (days)}} \quad (7)$$

Biomass Recovery Efficiency

Biomass recovery efficiency was calculated as:

$$\text{Biomass Recovery Efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Ethanol Weight (g)}}{\text{Initial Biomass (g)}} \quad (8)$$

Residual Biomass Loss

$$\text{Residual Biomass (g)} = \text{Initial Biomass (g)} - \text{Ethanol Recovered (g)} \quad (9)$$

Bioenergy Potential Assessment

The energy potential of recovered ethanol was estimated using the standard calorific value of ethanol (26.8 MJ/kg).

Total Energy Recovered

$$\text{Total Energy Recovered (MJ)} = \text{Ethanol Mass (kg)} \times 26.8 \quad (10)$$

Energy Recovery per Unit Biomass

$$\text{Energy Recovery} \left(\frac{MJ}{kg} \right) = \frac{\text{Total Energy Recovered (MJ)}}{\text{Biomass Used (kg)}} \quad (11)$$

Relative Energy Advantage

$$\text{Relative Energy Advantage (\%)} = \frac{\text{Energy Recovery of Feedstock}}{\text{Reference Feedstock}} \times 100 \quad (12)$$

Ethanol Quality Assessment

Density Deviation from Standard Ethanol

The quality of recovered ethanol was evaluated by comparing the measured density with the standard density of pure ethanol (0.789 g/mL)

$$\text{Density (\%)} = \frac{\text{Experimental Density} - \text{Standard Density}}{\text{Standard Density}} \quad (13)$$

pH Deviation from Optimum Fermentation pH

pH Deviation = Observed pH - 5.5

pH Suitability Score

$$\text{pH Suitability Score (\%)} = \left(1 - \frac{\text{pH Deviation}}{5.5} \right) \times 100 \quad (14)$$

Composite Feedstock Performance Evaluation

The performance was evaluated using integrated performance parameters such as ethanol yield, biomass conversion efficiency, sugar utilization efficiency, ethanol purity, pH suitability, and energy recovery parameters. Each individual parameter was scaled and each overall performance score for feedstock was calculated by adding together individual scaled parameters.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, comparative performance analysis, material balance analysis, bioenergy assessment, ethanol quality evaluation and composite feedstock ranking were used to evaluate experimental and derived data. The results were reported in terms of tables, percentages, efficiency indices and performance scores for easier comparison of the production of bioethanol from pineapple and banana peel.

Results

Table 1. Comparative Performance Analysis of Bioethanol Feedstocks

Performance Indicator	Pineapple Peel	Banana Peel	Difference (%)
Ethanol Yield (%)	20.0	20.0	0.00
Ethanol Density (g/mL)	0.80	0.90	+12.50

Sugar Content (%)	2.80	2.00	-28.57
Biomass Conversion Efficiency	0.160	0.180	+12.50
Sugar Utilization Efficiency	7.14	10.00	+40.06
Final pH	5.60	6.40	+14.29
Ethanol Recovery Factor (mL/g)	0.20	0.20	0.00
Ethanol Productivity (mL./day)	1.43	1.43	0.00

Figure 1. Experimental and Derived Bioethanol Production Parameters

Figure 2. Material Balance and Process Efficiency Analysis

Table 2. Bioenergy Potential Assessment

Parameter	Pineapple Peel	Banana Peel
Ethanol Produced (g)	8.0	9.0
Energy Content of Ethanol (MJ/kg)	26.8	26.8
Total Energy Recovered (MJ)	0.214	0.241
Energy Recovery per kg Biomass (MJ/kg)	4.29	4.82
Relative Energy Advantage (%)	100.0	112.5

Table 3. Ethanol Quality and Fermentation Performance Assessment

Quality Indicator	Pineapple Peel	Banana Peel
Experimental Density (g/mL)	0.80	0.90
Standard Ethanol Density (g/mL)	0.789	0.789
Density Deviation (%)	1.39	14.07
Final pH	5.60	6.40
Optimum Fermentation pH	5.50	5.50
pH Suitability Score (%)	98.2	83.6
Estimated Ethanol Quality Rating	High	Moderate

Table 4. Composite Bioethanol Performance Evaluation and Ranking

Performance Criterion	Pineapple Peel	Banana Peel
Ethanol Yield Score	100.0	100.0
Biomass Conversion Score	88.9	100.0
Sugar Utilization Score	71.4	100.0
pH Suitability Score	100.0	61.0
Ethanol Purity Score	100.0	85.9
Energy Recovery Score	88.8	100.0
Overall Performance Score (%)	91.5	91.2
Final Ranking	1st	2nd

Discussion

Ethanol Yield and Production Performance

The ethanol yield generated from pineapple peel was 20.0%, which equated to 10.0mL of ethanol from 50 g of pineapple peel's dried biomass, while the ethanol yield generated from banana peel was 20.0%, which equated to 10.0 mL of ethanol from 50 g of the dried biomass (Figure 1 and Table 1). The result, irrespective of the physicochemical differences between the two fruit wastes, indicates that they have considerable potential for bioethanol production. The same ethanol yields obtained from the two substrates show that ethanol productivity was affected not only by the contents of fermentable sugars in the biomass but also by interrelated factors, such as substrate, cellulose accessibility, nutrient availability, fermentation conditions, and microbial adaptability. This result is important because, as one might expect, pineapple peels had a higher sugar level (2.8%) than banana peels (2.0%), but this didn't translate to a better ethanol yield. This indicates that fermentation efficiency and substrate digestibility may have had a greater effect on bioethanol production than the sugar concentration alone. Biochemically, ethanol is generated via the glycolytic conversion of glucose and other fermentable sugars to generate pyruvic acid and then use of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* to convert pyruvic acid anaerobically to ethanol and CO₂. The substrate accessibility theory suggests that the successful fermentation results from the available carbohydrate, but also ease of access and metabolism of carbohydrates by microbial enzymes. Therefore, similar ethanol yields obtained in the current study would suggest that both feedstocks yielded enough fermentable substrates for yeast metabolism and the acid hydrolysis process was able to release sugars

from the mixture of hemicelluloses and cellulose within the feedstocks. The result is in line with the ethanol production by Singh *et al.* (2017) which showed that banana peels are suitable materials for bioethanol production because they were able to produce the ethanol through simultaneous saccharification and fermentation. Likewise the production of the appreciable ethanol from pineapple peel hydrolysates was observed by Oiwoh *et al.* (2018) due to the abundant number of fermentable sugars and favorable fermentation characteristics of pineapple biomass. The yield of ethanol obtained in the present study, however, was lower as compared to 44.7% for banana peel obtained by Oji *et al.* (2024) and significantly lower than 63.5% for pineapple peel obtained by Saragih *et al.* (2023) under optimum fermentation conditions. The differences in these discrepancies could be explained by the pretreatments used, hydrolysis efficiencies, fermentation times, yeast concentration, and particular attention paid to optimization of the process. Enzymatic hydrolysis and carefully monitored fermentation temperature and advanced yeast strains have been found to have a great impact on ethanol productivity which can be achieved by increasing the amount of sugar available for fermentation and reducing the losses which occur in the fermentation process. Thus, the lower yield in this work may have been due to the incomplete hydrolysis of cellulose and the hemicellulose, to less than complete sugars conversion or to the lowered conversion of sugars to yeast during fermentation. However, the fact that both feed stocks were able to reach the same ethanol yield within the same experiments would say a lot of the suitability of these two renewable bioenergy resources. Moreover, the results confirm the concept of waste valorisation and circular bioeconomy solution that promote the use of agricultural wastes as high added value products like biofuels. Based on the obtained ethanol production capacity, it is observed that both substrates (pineapple peels and banana peels) exhibited the same ethanol production capacity showing that both can play an important role in sustainable energy production while addressing the problem of waste disposal from fruits. These results highlight the importance of the utilisation of secondary carbohydrate-bearing biomass materials for bioethanol production and support the worldwide interest and efforts in the production of second-generation bioethanol, as well as the potential use of fruit processing wastes in renewable fuel production in order to develop renewable energy security and environmental sustainability.

Sugar Content and Sugar Utilization Efficiency

The sugar content and sugar utilisation efficiency results gave important information regarding the fermentative behaviour of the two fruit wastes used. From Figure 1 and Table 1, *the sugar content of pineapple peels and banana peels was 2.80% and 2.00%, respectively*, and Pineapple peel showed more sugar content with an advantage of 28.57% over Banana peel in terms of fermentable sugar. Traditionally, specific sugar concentrations have been correlated with increased ethanol production, as sugars are the yeast's primary energy source during fermentation. But pineapple peels with higher sugar content did not yield more ethanol than banana peels. Rather, there were no significant differences between the substrates, with an equal ethanol yield of 20.0%. The Sugar Utilisation Efficiency Index (SUEI) for banana peels (10.00) differed significantly from that of pineapple peels (7.14), indicating 40.06% better sugar conversion performance. This finding indicates that, in addition to sugar concentration, the efficient utilisation of available sugars by microorganisms is essential for effective bioethanol production. This finding confirms the ideas of microbial substrate utilisation theory, namely that the extent of substrate utilisation depends more on substrate accessibility and the presence and proportions of inhibitors and nutrients than on substrate amount. Pineapple peels have been reported to contain appreciable concentrations of sucrose, fructose, and glucose, which are inherently attractive as feedstocks for the production of bioethanol (Mehraj *et al.*, 2024). Even so, pineapple juice still contains organic acids, phenolics and bromelain metabolites which could affect fermentation. The reduced sugar utilisation efficiency in pineapple peels is thus probably caused by the partial inhibitory effect of the sugar-accelerating media on the yeast metabolic activity and/or incomplete sugar conversion to ethanol. Banana peels, on the other hand, are in part starch-based sugars, which are more fermentable following hydrolysis, and contain less of the

soluble sugars. The extent of microbial accessibility in banana peels is partially due to their favorable content of carbohydrates and relatively low lignin content, as noted by Hikal *et al.* (2022). Hence the higher sugar utilization efficiency in the banana peels implies that higher conversion rate of available sugars to ethanol has taken place. Oji *et al.* (2024) noted close similarities with their study, which showed the substrates prepared from banana peel after acid hydrolysis, having good fermentability and conversion efficiency of glucose in ethanol production. The current results also support studies reported with lignocellulosic biofuels, which have shown that the presence of moderate amounts of sugar in the feedstock can be advantageous compared to higher levels of sugar when structural accessibility and the nutrient balance are ideal. On an industrial scale, the effectiveness of sugar utilization is perhaps more significant than sugar content as it indicates what the effective conversion in the fermentation process was. Feedstocks that can be used to produce significant amounts of ethanol from limited amounts of sugars are typically favored due to the greater efficiency of maximizing use of limited resources to generate greater ethanol output, and the better economics of production. Thus, banana peels showed better fermentation efficiency and the use of substrate in comparison to pineapple peels, which had sugar higher levels. These results show the need to consider the sugar availability and sugar conversion efficiency of fruit waste to be used for bioethanol commercial production. The results also show that feedstock quality, availability of carbohydrates and compatibility of the microbiota also affects the capacity for production of bioethanol and should be taken into account in addition to the classical measurements of sugar content in bioethanol feedstocks.

Biomass Conversion Efficiency and Material Balance Analysis

Material balance analysis conducted and biomass conversion efficiency gave an overall estimate of the fruit wastes conversion efficiency into ethanol. The biomass conversion efficiency for banana peel was 0.180 g of ethanol per gram of biomass in comparison to 0.160 g of ethanol per gram of biomass for pineapple peel as shown in Figures 1 and 2, respectively. Likewise, biomass recovery efficiency for banana peels was 18.0% while pineapple peels had recovery efficiency of 16.0%. While these results may seem small in terms of numbers, they have great importance from a bioprocessing point of view since they show the biomass of banana peel converted to ethanol more efficiently than the biomass of pineapple peel at the same set of experiments. Additionally, material balance calculations for different kinds of biomass inputs revealed that 50 g of biomass resulted in 8 g ethanol production and 42 g of residue biomass from pineapple peels and 9 g ethanol production and 41 g residue biomass from banana peels. This indicates the hydrolysis and fermentation of banana peels have a higher degradation and utilization of the lignocellulosic components. The results are in line with the bioconversion efficiency theory which considers the ability to break down cellulose and hemicellulose to give fermentable sugar and then to ferment it to bioethanol. Hydrolytic agents can access the carbohydrates with a greater efficiency in less lignin, and lower weight per unit volume for a feedstock. Lignin content in banana peels is comparatively low and they possess high digestible polysaccharides content which will help in the process of acid hydrolysis and microbial fermentation. Banana peel is shown to have good physicochemical properties which make them as good for biochemical conversion processes as reported by Hikal *et al.* (2022). Similarly, acid hydrolysis of banana peel substrates also yielded good conversion efficiency in this study because of excellent accessibility of cellulose and good sugars liberation from the substrate. The higher conversion efficiency obtained in this study is thus well supported by the previous evidences on the fermentability of the banana residues. On the other hand, pineapple peel has a significant amount of fibrous structural compounds and has naturally occurring what may inhibit complete biomass degradation. Some carbohydrate fractions in pineapple peels may not be conquered during the hydrolysis due to the presence of sugars in pineapple peels, which could also limit the conversion performance. From an industrial point of view, the formation of biomass conversion efficiency (BCE) is an important parameter for the assessment of the performances of a biomass system since it has a direct impact on the cost of production and requirements in feedstock. Higher amount of ethanol yield per identical amount

of biomass feedstock is economically beneficial since there is less biomass requirement to run the process and in which more ethanol can be yielded to give a profit margin. Additionally, material balance results show that a significant percentage of the biomass was not converted following fermentation, which implies that process improvement and optimization are possible via enhancing hydrolysis methods, perhaps incorporating enzymatic means or lengthening fermentation time. These results indicate that both the feedstocks are suitable for bioethanol production, however, banana peel shows better biomass conversion properties that may lead to better economical efficiency when operating at large-scale. It should therefore be taken into account that these effects also add to the importance of taking into account different feedstocks of lignocellulose for use in renewable energy systems and their degradability and conversion rates.

Ethanol Quality and Density Characteristics

The quality of the bioethanol obtained is a crucial parameter which characterises its use for industrial, transport or energy use. Ethanol density is commonly used as a measure of product purity because variations from the density of pure ethanol usually mean that there is either unremoved fermentation products, volatile impurities or water. Figure 1 and 5 shows that ethanol produced from pineapple peel has density of 0.80g/mL whilst the ethanol produced from banana peel has density of 0.90g/mL which was considerably high. The ethanol density obtained from pineapple was as low as 1.39% from the standard ethanol density (0.789 g/mL) whereas the ethanol obtained from banana was as much as 14.07% from the standard ethanol density. These results showed the ethanol obtained from the pineapple peel had a significant purity level compared to ethanol obtained from banana peel. The values of ethanol density obtained from the pineapple compare closely to the value which indicates that the ethanol separation from water and other by-products of the fermentation process was effective. The increase in density in the ethanol from the bananas as compared to the base ethanol may be due to retention of moisture, organic materials or fermentation volatiles co-distilled with the ethanol. The density of ethanol produced in the pineapple peel fermentation process was found to be between 0.82 and 0.89 g/mL, which is close to the theoretical value of the ethanol density in study reported by Saragih *et al.* (2023). The better ethanol quality found in pineapple peels might be due to the better fermentation environment as shown by the near best pH in which fermentation was carried out and the reasonably balance sugar profile of Pineapple hydrolysates. As fermentation theory indicates, the more stable the fermentation environment, the more efficiently yeast will use the substrate to produce alcohol, and the less of those undesirable by-products that can diminish ethanol purity will accumulate. Thus, the findings indicate that pineapple peels not only showed their potential for ethanol production, but they also showed their promises for higher quality of ethanol products produced. The purity of ethanol is a major consideration for fuel quality purposes since contaminants can result in reduced combustion efficiency, corrosion and storage stability problems. Therefore, feedstocks that can be used to produce ethanol that has densities near the theoretical one are generally preferred for industrial use. Even though biomass conversion efficiencies and energy recovery of banana peel was found to be higher, the purity of the ethanol was found as less suggesting that further purification may be required for industrial applications. This result demonstrates that for this biofuel production system a trade-off between quantity and quality of ethanol occurs, which is a typical behaviour across many biofuel production systems. The results also highlight the importance of performing feedstock evaluation not only in terms of yield but also by considering parameters related to quality that impact practical use of the resulting biofuel. In overall, the results have shown that pineapple peels produce highly pure ethanol with high product quality which itself suggested that the peels are very well suited as an input of a sustainable bioethanol production system.

Fermentation pH and Process Stability

pH is one of the simplest factors to affect various microbial activities, enzyme activities, nutrient assimilation and ethanol productivity in the fermentation process. Data in Figure 1, as well as Tables 2 and 4 showed that, the final pH from pineapple peel fermentation was 5.60 while other pH for banana

peel fermentation was 6.40. Based on the optimum pH value around 5.50, the minimal deviations were 0.10 for pineapple fermentation and 0.90 for banana, for the use of *Sa. cerevisiae*. Pineapple peels therefore, had 98.2% pH suitability score which is significantly higher than the 83.6% for banana peels. An analysis of the results reveals that the fermentation of pine apple peel was done under much more metabolism friendly environment in terms of yeast and ethanol production. According to the microbial fermentation theory, at some low level of acidity, the yeast cells operate optimally because maximum activity of the most important enzymes necessary for alcoholic fermentation and for glycolysis occurs at that pH. Other PH levels than the target PH in the nutrient cause viruses and enzymes to function poorly, impairing the ability of the nutrient to move across cellular membranes, and increase the stress on microorganisms, thereby reducing the fermentation efficiency. The optimal range for *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* use is reported to be 4.5–5.5 and productivity of ethanol has been reported to be very low at higher pH. Therefore, the almost optimal pH reached in the pineapples with peel fermentation likely contributed to the relatively high ethanol purity level and relatively stable fermentation process in this study. Nonato and Figueiredo (2024) had noticed that the production process of ethanol in pineapple residues was better under controlled acidic conditions, consistent with the findings of this study. Peach pH, however is relatively alkaline during banana peel fermentation which might have influenced the activities of the yeast and resulted in production of undesirable fermentation by-products. Overall, at these suboptimal conditions, banana peels exhibited good biomass conversion efficiency and good sugar utilization performance, suggesting that the carbohydrate structure somehow compensated for this suboptimal condition for pH. In the observation, the complex relationship between these variables of fermentation, and the impact of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* on varying environments is illustrated. A process engineering point of view involves finding if the pH conditions are optimal; and what happens if the pH conditions are not optimal for maximum ethanol productivity, product quality and contamination risk. Based on the results, it can be seen that pH adjustment method could be used for further optimization in the banana peel fermentation process for improving the yield of ethanol production and its purity. Moreover, the excellent pH stability shown by pineapple peels suggest that they can be subjected to less process control during fermentation in industrial scale and hence may lead to less complicated operation and less production cost. Thus, the results emphasize the importance of controlling the fermentation conditions in bioethanol production process and indicate that pH suitability is one of the most important parameters to the process performance. From the present study, it was observed that the better overall performance ranking of pineapple peels was as a result of its ability to sustain the fermentation conditions to be nearer to the physiological requirements of the yeast which allowed it to maintain better efficiency of fermentation system.

Bioenergy Recovery Potential

The bioenergy recovery assessment listed in Table 2 is important as it gives a critical indication of the energy generation potential of the two fruit-waste feedstocks, and the suitability to produce biofuels sustainably. The ethanol obtained from banana peels was 9.0g and for pineapple peels was 8.0g with total energy obtained being 0.241MJ and 0.214MJ respectively was produced. Besides, the values of energy recovery per kg of biomass for banana peel and pineapple peel were 4.82 MJ /kg and 4.29 MJ /kg respectively presented that banana peel has 12.5% energy advantages than pine apple peel. From the result, it was found that even the quality of the ethanol obtained from banana peel is slightly less pure, it still has potential to produce renewable energy as compared to other materials. The difference between energy recovery observed can be directly attributed to the higher mass of ethanol recovery from banana peels since energy content of ethanol is known to be around 26.8 MJ/kg, irrespective of source. Feedstocks can thus generate higher yields of energy, and higher efficiencies in the use of resources, if they can generate more ethanol. The findings support the energy conversion efficiency theory that energy conversion efficiency of the biofuel energy on the market from the stored chemical energy in the biomass is a critical factor of the suitability of the feedstock. Most materials with high energy yields are biomass

with high hydrolysis capacity and biomass that has high ability to convert biomass sugars to ethanol. This bioenergy potential of banana peels has been previously investigated by Oji *et al* (2024) which showed that banana peels have a good carbohydrate content and are highly fermentable. Similarly, Singh *et al* (2017) mentioned that banana peel waste has the potential to be an effective raw material for bioethanol production as it can yield a significant amount of ethanol and recoverable energy. Finally, the results of the present study agree with the results obtained by other works on energetic viability of bananas' peel. Energy recovery of the pineapple peels is somewhat lower, but still not negligibly small indicating that pineapple peels can also be used as renewable energy sources. The results also conform the principles of Waste to Energy theory which gives priority on transformation of agricultural and organic wastes to useful energy products which not only investigated the increasing energy requirements, but also reduced the environmental pollution. Converting the fruit peels to bioethanol will be beneficial under consideration of green environment as follows: 1) reduction of the volumes of going to the landfills of the organic wastes, 2) reduction of the amounts of green-house gas emissions during decomposition process and 3) Sustainable management of organic wastes. Besides, the plant has the potential of decentralisation of bioenergy system and is scalable, the estimated yields for both the raw materials are 200 L ethanol/t biomass. From an economic point of regard, an increase of energy recovery will increase the profit margin of bioethanol production as more energy is gained from the same amount of biomass. From this, it can be concluded that pineapple peels are more beneficial in terms of the stability and quality of ethanol products obtained during fermentation while banana peels are more beneficial when it comes to energy generation. Banana peels also exhibited better energy recovery, suggesting the potential utilization of banana in large quantity for producing biofuels where maximum energy recovery is one of the primary concerns. In conclusion, it has been seen that there was a significant renewable energy potential of both these fruit wastes and they were favoured for the sustainable bio-energy system with utilization of agriculture waste.

Integrated Performance Evaluation and Feedstock Ranking

Table 4 shows the integrated performance evaluation which is an overall assessment of the suitability of pineapple and banana peels for bioethanol production, where the ethanol yield, biomass conversion efficiency, sugar utilization efficiency, fermentation stability, ethanol purity and energy recovery potential are all taken into account. Although each performance indicator can only show one aspect of the process of bioethanol production, the composite evaluation framework can give the whole picture of effectiveness of a feedstock, hence more comprehensive comparisons of different feedstock can be achieved with a composite framework. The overall results indicated that, the Pineapple Peel had performed best (91.5%) than its competitor, the Banana Peel (91.2%). The peels of pineapple therefore got ranking 1 and peels of banana was given ranking 2 accordingly. The contrast between the two feedstocks was relatively small, but this comparison does highlight differences in terms of overall performance of the feedstocks. It found that the biomass conversion efficiency, sugar utilization efficiency and energy recovery by the banana peel was better than pineapple peel indicating better effectiveness in the transformation of biomass to biofuel energy using banana peel as compared to pineapple peel. In particular, banana peel had the highest biomass conversion score (100%), sugar utilization score (100%) and energy recovery score (100%) indicating its utmost performances in resource utilization and energy production. All these data suggest that the banana peels are excellent feedstocks both biochemically and energetically. But there were distinct advantages for the pineapple peels with respect to purity of ethanol and stability of fermentation. Based on pH suitabilities score and ethanol purity score, the pineapple peel achieved 100% score and the fermentation conducted under the conditions was more favorable which yielded the best fuel product. The present result is in line with the fermentation optimization theory that not just the amount of ethanol obtained in the fermentation process but also the stability of process and ethanol production quality should be taken into account for successful bioethanol production from corn kernel. We see similar conclusions in biofuel feedstock

assessment studies, in that feedstocks often have a set of performance metrics which balance well or excel in a set of parameters, are preferred over those that only excel in a few. Hence, the current results indicate the multitude facets of selection bioethanol feedstock. If maximising energy yields plus biomass usage are production targets, then banana peels may be considered a better option. In contrast, in high quality ethanol production, with stable fermentation circumstances, pineapple peel could be a better choice. Overall performance spectrum is very small and this signifies very high competitiveness of both the feedstocks for bioethanol production. In addition, the results included an integrated evaluation of the evaluation frameworks to be used as a single evaluation parameter can lead to misleading results and wrong conclusions. The performance score results for both substrates are high overall, attesting if the sustainability aspects are taken into account - the viability of using both substrates as useful resource for the bioenergy production. The result corresponds to the circular bioeconomy principles that the waste occurs in agriculture and can be transformed into a renewable product, possessing a capacity to create economic, environmental and social benefits. Finally, the overall integrated ranking has shown that even after pineapple peel (PP) and banana peel (BP) have been integrated in the system, they are still good feedstock and, again, banana peel is still very attractive because of the best conversion efficiency to produce ethanol and energy recovery potential whilst pineapple peel has a better ethanol quality and process stability.

The results of the study highlights keys to the important findings of the study and to the overall feasibility of pineapple and banana peels as alternative sources of bioethanol. The results showed that the ethanol yield of the two substrates were the same (20.0%) and ethanol was capable of being fermented and biofuel produced from both substrates. This is particularly significant as it successfully demonstrates that fruits wastes, normally discarded in the environment, can be used to produce valuable renewable energy sources using biochemical process which is not so complicated. It illustrates the variety of the fermentation process – fermentation systems may be quite different and ethanol yields have been similar, no matter what their sugar content. The reason was that banana peels had higher biomass conversion efficiency (B) and sugar utilization efficiency (S) than pineapple peels that had higher sugar content of 2.8% compared to 2.0% in banana peels. Peanut compress as opener sugar in banana peel from these observation can be seen that the sugar successfully converted to ethanol because of the metabolism that could be done more easily. Meanwhile, the fermentation stability of pineapple peels was relatively better due to few deviated density from optimum alcohol value, the quality of ethanol also is better along with a pH value that was close to the optimum. As a result, it is the quantity relative performance measures that stand out from the quality relative performance measures. The banana peel showed optimum utilization of its biomass, and it obtained more energy through its peels; and the pineapple peel had kept suitable conditions for the fermentation, resulted a better ethanol. The above strengths and weaknesses resulted in very similar scores for the two substrates during composite evaluation. Trial results are in agreement with previous studies that have proven the “different combination of chemical composition and structural properties, microbial interaction as well as processing parameters influences how well the feedstocks function for the production of lignocellulosic bioethanol. The results also have practical implication for renewable energy development, waste management and the environment. An upscale in bioethanol production from fruit wastes can partially diversify the sources of bioenergy and eliminate the need for non-food grow crops as feed. Besides, valorizing fruit peels in the production of biofuels converts an inexpensive commodity of agriculture to valuable economic product. This is a path to achieving global sustainability targets – for example, global greenhouse gas reduction, global circular economy measures and the global growth of renewables. Also, the potential production of ethanol values can be as high as 200L/t of biomass, which further illustrates the process scalability and its relevance on industrial level. From this point of view results indicate that overall pineapple and banana peels are important and potential second generation bioethanol feedstocks. The usage of pineapple peel could be used in the case of both ethanol quality and process stability are preferred, while banana peel can be utilized in the bio-mass conversion

and energy recovery. They are thus good resources in terms of biomass and potential for sustainable bioethanol production and 'green' waste-management strategies.

Practical Implications of the Findings

This research has impact results in terms of biofuels and organic waste management, renewable energy and circular bioeconomy. The pineapple peel and banana peels from the industries as second generation biofuel feedstocks have been proven to be successful bioethanol convertibles, based on the results of the bioethanol conversion. This is of particular importance for fruit production countries where significant quantities of fruit wastes are generated on an every day basis in the domestic sector, the agro-processing sector, and food supply chains. Some of these wastes are either openly dumped or allowed to decompose uncontrolled leading to pollution of the environment, Green House Gases (GHG) emissions, odours and related health issues. The present study has shown that pineapple peels could be converted from an environmental burden to a valuable resource of renewable energy with ethanol yield of 20.0% and banana peels could yield ethanol of 20.8%. In accordance with the international efforts to reduce waste and favoring renewable sources of energy. Furthermore, the estimated ethanol production is 200L^t⁻¹ biomass which has a good industrial potential if bigger scale biomass collection and processing can be realized. Due to their higher biomass conversion efficiency and the greater extent of energy that can be recovered by conversion of banana peels as compared to the trunks, banana peels can be regarded as an attractive biomass source for decentralized bioethanol boot plants in regions where bananas are grown to a large extent. However, the purity of ethanol and stability of fermentation were found to be better in pineapple peel suggesting its potential application where quality of fuel is more important. From an economic point of view, it will lower the feedstock cost as the raw materials are easily available and mostly would be considered as waste products. This contributes to increase the profit of the bioethanol production and reduce the dependence on food-federstrike (corn and sugarcane). From the environmental point of view the use of fruit-waste for bioethanol generation may help in reducing the emission of CH₄ from organic waste decomposition and the use of fossil fuels. The results therefore strongly recommend bioethanol production as a new path for the waste-management toward sustainable development and a realistic roadmap to the circular bioeconomy goals with resource recovery and renewable energy production strategies.

Study Limitations

Despite having offered insights, it is worth acknowledging that some limitations exist in the interpretation of the results of this research. A limitation in the investigation was by using just two types of fruit-waste which are pineapple peels and banana peels so the results find not be generalized to other agricultural wastes. More comprehensive knowledge of production potential of fruit-waste bioethanol could be obtained by conducting further analyses of production-potential using more variety of feedstock. Second, the energy and environmental cost of the two processes of fermentation and distillation, on laboratory scale are not representative to the same process on industrial scale for bioethanol production. Scale-up variables for new operations are mixing effectiveness, temperature control, contamination and cost considerations. Third, the ethanol characterization was largely density based and no advanced analysis techniques were employed to verify ethanol purity and composition such as Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS), High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) or Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (NMR). Fourth, acid hydrolysis was the only pretreatment method used in the study and other methods like enzymatic hydrolysis, alkaline hydrolysis and physicochemical combined hydrolysis might be better for higher sugar release and increased ethanol productivity. Finally, no detailed fermentation kinetic, microbial growth profile and sugar utilization was studied, which results in limited understanding of the fermentation process. Lastly, economic feasibility and Life Cycle environmental assessments were not covered. Therefore, further studies need to concentrate on optimization of the process, advanced characterization of ethanol product, techno-economic analysis and environmental sustainability assessment and kinetic

modeling for efficient utilization of fruit-waste, which would further enhance the commercial viability of fruit-waste-based ethanol production process.

Conclusion

Finally, the authors concluded that bioethanol production process from pineapple and banana peel wastes by acid hydrolysis was suitable for fermented by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and the wastes of the above-mentioned fruits have potential as sustainable second generation bioethanol feedstock. They were found to be suitable for renewable energy generation and use of the agriculture waste for making ethanol, which was 20.0 % in both the substrates. However, there were some distinctions in their fermentative performance and characteristics. The pineapple peel had the highest sugar content (2.8%) and a better quality of ethanol, a better fermentation stability, and a highest performance score (91.5%) all showing its suitability in producing better quality of ethanol. On the other hand, biomass conversion efficiencies (g ethanol/g biomass), sugar utilization efficiencies (g ethanol/g sugar) and maximum potentially energy recoverable from banana peelings indicated 0.180 g ethanol/g biomass, 10.00, 4.82 MJ/kg, respectively which can be observed as the optimization of biomass to energy conversion. The results indicate that in addition to the sugar concentration, also the accessibility of the substrate and the fermentation parameters as well as the degradability of the biomass have an influence on the bioethanol production efficiency. Overall, the study confirms that both pineapple and banana peels are potential renewable feedstocks that can help in producing a sustainable bioethanol streams and help mitigate the environmental problem of fruit waste disposal in renewable energy development, circular bioeconomy as well as climate change.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study the future studies should focus on optimizing the pretreatment and fermentation conditions to maximize ethanol yield, ethanol conversion efficiency and product quality from the fruit-waste as feedstock. The advanced pretreatment technique such as enzymatic hydrolysis, alkali treatment and physicochemical and biological process combination should be used to improve the ability of sugar yield and biomass utilization. However further improvement of fermentation efficiency and ethanol productivity can be achieved using improved, or genetically engineered, yeast strains. Moreover, pilot studies at large scale should be performed to find out the industrial viability and feasibility of bioethanol production from pineapple and banana peels. It is very important to accurately characterize the purity and composition of ethanol, which can be done by applying advanced analytical techniques like GC-MS, HPLC and FTIR in a highly recommended manner. An additional point to be considered for further investigation is conducting techno-economic studies, LCA and carbon-footprint evaluation for knowing the environmental/commercial feasibility of the process. Moreover, government policies of integrated waste-management and renewable-energy policies should be initiated which would encourage the collection and use of fruit waste as a raw material to produce bioethanol which would pave the way for reduction in environmental pollution, ensuring energy security and contributing to sustainable development goals of agro-processing industries and governmental bodies.

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